

PHYSIOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF SPORTS AND MOVEMENT GAMES FOR CHILDREN DURING PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Now days, preschool education is a part of uninterrupted education. A healthy generation is the starting point of children's journey to a great life. This article explains in a broad sense that in order to impart modern knowledge, a coach must first properly organize the educational process only when he is well acquainted with the physiological mastery of the growing and developing generation at different times.*

Keywords: *Physiology, hygiene, pedagogue, healthy generation, growth, development, heterophony, acceleration, heredity, environment, dominant, recessive, chromosome, gene, mutation, hereditary diseases.*

INTRODUCTION

Special features of the child's nervous system. Studying the age-related laws of the development of the child's central nervous system is of particular importance in the implementation of full-fledged physical education of children of primary and preschool age. This pedagogical influence helps to choose forms and organize the educational process. According to scientists, a child comes into the world with his innate abilities and features of the nervous system. However, they are the organic ground of the child's mental development and do not determine the nature and level of this development. It has also been proven that every child has great potential psychophysiological capabilities that form a reliable basis for their neuro-spiritual development. Thus, taking into account the organic ground on the one hand and the potential opportunities on the other hand, it is necessary to create the most favorable pedagogical conditions, to properly organize the physical education process that allows direct influence on the child's organism and psyche in the conditions of goal-oriented upbringing and education. Taking into account the characteristics of the child's innate nervous system and the leading role of external influence in its formation, it is important to ensure the correct order (good sleep, clearly defining the volume of training, active movement activities, time spent in the open air) and its consistent implementation. In this case, a positive emotional situation - children's mutual and adults' calm, friendly relations with children at the same time are of particular importance. Physiologist N.I. Krosnagorskiy according to: "Adult role models, the environment, and the environment as a whole are important factors in the development of the higher nervous system. Different forms of children's whims arise in a situation of dissatisfaction, excitement, and quarrels, and treating the child with restraint in all respects is a good means of forming a firm, complete character."

In the process of physical education, children's typological characteristics are taken into account in order to approach them in an individual order, optimal conditions for order, training, active movement activities, and the emotional positive state of the child. Personal observations of the educator in the daily life process are very important. Current analysis helps the educator to

draw the necessary conclusions and maintain the child's emotional state, develop various active activities, and determine ways to show creative inclinations. Physical education has practical means and methods of influencing the comprehensive development of a child's personality. In the process of active action activity, the child practices the manifestation of moral and willful qualities: he acts courageously despite the risk of being caught in the game, he strives to help his friend, to do the common work together with everyone (for example, to run on time and line up with all the children) and others. When such an action is repeated several times, the child perceives it as a necessity, the encouraging evaluation of the educator and peers instills in the child a sense of spiritual satisfaction, emotional upliftment, and the desire to continue such actions in the future. A shy child playing leading roles and showing and explaining to all children how to perform an exercise according to the teacher's instructions gradually saves him from shyness, sharpens his memory, and arouses interest in training. The child becomes more polite, proactive and cheerful. Systematic development of creative initiative in a child should be considered an integral part of physical education. Movement activities in physical games and physical exercises help to manifest this initiative. The creative tasks given to (children) in these forms of action strengthen the development of imagination and thinking, the birth of association and the desire to invent something, and then the desire to put one's intention into practice. (L.M. Korovina, E.Y. Stepanenkova).

“Care for human health, especially child health,” he wrote V.A. Suxomlinskiy, – it is not only a complex of sanitary-hygiene norms and rules, a set of requirements for order, food, work, and rest. This is, first of all, the care of the harmonious balance of all physical and spiritual forces, and the crown of harmony is the pleasure and joy of creativity”.

METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING AND CONDUCTING ACTION GAMES.

The teacher's mastery of the method of leading the game process is the main condition for successful games. Action games are selected and planned according to the program. It takes into account the working conditions of each age group, such as the general level of physical and mental development of children, the development of movement skills, the health status of each child, its own characteristics, the season, daily routine, the place of the house, as well as the specific characteristics of children's interests. Action games are gradually becoming more complicated in accordance with the requirements of the program, they are changed taking into account the growth of children's minds, the movement experience they have gained, and the need to prepare them for school.

In senior groups, the educator prepares children to independently organize active games, while monitoring the progress of the games and especially the fulfillment of the rules, as well as the relationships between children. He gives children tasks such as inventing variants of a mobile game by changing its content, rules, game actions, and then finding a new game by himself. In order to educate the children of the large group of independence and organizational skills, the educator offers them to organize a game with the children of the small group. The game is played under the supervision of a small group educator. Active games are important in the comprehensive education of children. No matter how the game activity is expressed, it pleases the child and evokes positive feelings in them. Action games expand a child's worldview and are a unique tool for learning about the environment. The rules of action games determine the course of the game, organize children's movement activities, mutual relations, and help to educate moral and willful qualities. It is important for every child to understand the rules of the game and to be guided by adults.

Moral qualities such as honesty, justice, friendship, bravery, self-control, determination is brought up in children through games. In game activities, favorable conditions are created for the development of attention, perception, clarification of thinking, understanding and target acquisition, games help to develop creative imagination, memory, ingenuity, thinking activity. Thus, active games help the child's mental development. Due to the game activity, the child practically learns the reality of space and objects, and at the same time, he also improves the mechanism of space perception.

For example, the child's independent choice of the direction of movement and execution of his movement in the direction strictly defined by the rules of the game, on the one hand, immediately evaluates the game situation (directly perceived) and visual-motor reaction (game actions), and on the other hand, awareness and imagination of his actions in the space-game environment requires doing. Action games form a simple time frame in children. They are expressed in the following: in understanding the sequence of game actions, it is seen in the rapid performance of game tasks, such as first, then, next, before, all at the same time, according to the signal, within the time limit set for children. In these games, children practice aiming in space, consistency of actions and following them over time. Independent explanation of the content of games, the entire game situation, its rules, the actions of characters, showing children's location, game attributes and directions of movement using spatial expressions, evaluating the played game serves the mental development of children. Action games facilitate the development of creativity in older children. In this case, children can invent small games based on the content of the stories they have heard. Movement games are aesthetic activities based on their content and form. The variety of game actions is expressed by the children's clear agility and unique expressiveness. The use of music in action games has great aesthetic value.

When conducting action games, one should not forget the beauty and culture of actions: it is necessary to pay attention to the children whose actions are somewhat expressive, to encourage those who can express the images expressively and successfully. It is a complex activity consisting of various emotional movements. This activity is performed in conditions and situations that suddenly change based on established rules. Action games differ in the features of organizing and managing the activities of the participants. During the game, movement in suddenly changing situations and physical qualities such as quickness, agility (distraction, avoiding "traps") are manifested. During the game, children's activities are organized on the basis of a figurative plot

or game tasks, and this is positive for the child to perform physical exercises with enthusiasm and for a long time. This, in turn, enhances their effect on the body and helps develop endurance. Observing the rules of the game helps to cultivate moral qualities (mutual help, conscious discipline). A combination of various complex actions (running, jumping) is seen in game activity. The use of games, especially in work with children of preschool age, gives good results. Action games are an important complex educational process.

Children's movement activity, which is the basis of this process, has a positive effect on physical development, the formation of movement skills and physical qualities, the strengthening of health by increasing the functional activity of the body and enhancing feelings of emotional joy. Action games, as one of the main means and methods of physical education, help to effectively solve the tasks listed above. The healing effect achieved by active games is inextricably linked with the positive emotions that arise during children's game activities and have a positive effect on the child's psyche.

Emotional excitement awakens children's desire to achieve a goal common to all, and it is expressed in a clear understanding of tasks, mutual compatibility of actions, accurate targeting in space and game conditions, and accelerated execution of tasks. Due to children's strong desire to achieve the goal and enjoyable pursuit, the role of willpower, which helps to overcome various obstacles, increases. Active games serve as a method of improving previously acquired movement skills and physical qualities of children. During the game, the child focuses on achieving the goal, not on the method of performing the action. It adapts to the conditions of the game, showing agility and thus improving the movements. Therefore, for example, the game "Wolf in the ravine" is given after children learn to run and long jump. As a movement activity, movement play has certain special characteristics: it requires the child to respond quickly to signals and sudden changes in the game.

Various situations and actions occurring in the game require changes in the level of muscle tension. For example, in the "Trap" game, each child should carefully follow the actions of the leader: when the leader approaches him, he quickly runs away in the opposite direction; when he feels safe, he moves slowly and stops; accelerates again when the starter approaches. Almost every action game has actions and cues for children's movements. Such active movement activities train the child's nervous system, improving and balancing the processes of excitation and inhibition, as well as observation, ingenuity, the ability to aim in a changing environment, find a way out of a difficult situation, quickly make a decision and implement it, ingenuity, Agility teaches initiative, choosing an independent way to achieve a goal.

The origin of action games goes back to ancient folk pedagogy. Children of early age are brought up in families with the help of toys and fun games related to the child's initial movements. In the life of children older than that, folk games with colorful action content occupy a great place in children's lives. All of these still retain their artistic appeal, educational value and constitute valuable gaming folklore.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, if a young organism develops healthy from the very beginning, it will not affect the efficiency of future activities. Its gene pool is also important for the development of a young organism. For the healthy development of every organism, of course, a healthy diet, a properly structured agenda and, of course, exercise are necessary.

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